

The Tapes:

Path, Territoriality and Re-signification in the Historical-Cultural Formation of Southern Brazil

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Abstract

This article analyzes the origin, meaning and historical implications of the term "Tapes", derived from the Tupi-Guarani word *tapé*, which means "path", "trail" or "road".¹ From this etymological basis, the relationship between language, territoriality and identity of the Guarani groups that inhabited plateau regions west of Lagoa dos Patos, in present-day southern Brazil, this study investigates. These groups, later called "Tapes", were associated with a strategic area of circulation that connected the interior to the coast, configuring themselves as an important axis of mobility and exchange before and during the colonial period.

The research also addresses the process of consolidation of the so-called "Tape zone", as well as the formation of Jesuit reductions from 1626 onwards, under the action of the Society of Jesus, which contributed to the spatial and sociocultural reorganization of these peoples. It also analyzes the subsequent appropriation and re-signification of the term "Tapes" by the Portuguese colonizers and bandeirantes, evidencing its transformation from a designation linked to indigenous mobility to a generic category of territorial and ethnic identification.

Methodologically, the study is based on bibliographic review and historical analysis of a qualitative nature, dialoguing with contributions from historiography, anthropology and linguistics. As a result, a critical reading of the construction of the term "Tapes" this article proposes, understanding it not only as a geographical or ethnic denomination, but as an expression of power dynamics, circulation and symbolic dispute in the process of historical formation of southern Brazil.

Keywords

Tapes; Guarani; Territoriality; Indigenous paths; Jesuit Missions; History of Southern Brazil.

¹ MELIÀ, Bartomeu. *The Guarani conquered and reduced*, 1986.

1. Introduction

The historical formation of southern Brazil is deeply linked to the territorial and cultural dynamics of indigenous peoples that preceded the European colonial occupation. In this context, the presence of the Guarani groups that inhabited extensive areas of the current territory of Rio Grande do Sul stands out, especially in the plateau regions located west of the Patos Lagoon. Among these groups are those that were later called "Tapes", whose identification refers to the Tupi-Guarani term *tapé*, which means "path", "trail" or "road".²

The notion of *tapé*, in addition to its linguistic dimension, expresses a conception of space associated with mobility, circulation and interconnection between different territories. In this sense, the so-called Tapes cannot be understood only as an ethnic subgroup of the Guarani, but also as part of a territorial network structured by paths that articulated the interior of the continent with the coast. This condition gave the region a strategic role both in the pre-colonial period and during European expansion, being recognized as a zone of passage and exchange.

From the seventeenth century, with the action of the Society of Jesus and the foundation of missionary reductions — especially from 1626 — the region came to be known as "Missions of the Tapes" or "Serra dos Tapes".³ This process implied significant transformations in the spatial and sociocultural organization of indigenous groups, introducing new forms of territorialization and control. At the same time, the intensification of the bandeirante incursions contributed to the dismantling of these missions and to the reconfiguration of the local populations.

In this scenario, the term "Tapes" went through a process of expansion and re-signification, being incorporated into the Portuguese colonial vocabulary as a generic designation both for the indigenous people of the region and for the territory itself. Such a transformation evidences not only a semantic change, but also a movement of symbolic appropriation, in which original categories are reinterpreted in the light of colonial interests.

In view of this, the main problem of this article is to understand how the term "Tapes", originally linked to the notion of path in the Tupi-Guarani universe, was appropriated and re-signified throughout the colonial process, and what are the implications of this transformation for the understanding of identity and territorial occupation in southern Brazil. As a general objective, it seeks to analyze the historical and semantic evolution of this denomination, considering its relationship with indigenous territoriality and with the power dynamics that marked the colonization of the region.

Specifically, it is intended to investigate the linguistic origin of the term *Tapé*; to understand the territorial organization of the Guarani groups associated with the Tapes; to analyze the importance of the region as an axis of circulation between the interior and the coast; and to examine the role of the Jesuit missions in the reconfiguration of these

²MELIÀ, Bartomeu. *The Guarani conquered and reduced*, 1986.

³KERN, Arno Alvarez. *Missions: a political utopia*, 1982.

spaces. To this end, the research adopts a qualitative approach, based on bibliographic review and historical analysis, dialoguing with contributions from historiography, anthropology and linguistics.

By proposing a critical reading of the construction of the term "Tapes", this study seeks to contribute to the debate about indigenous protagonism in the historical formation of southern Brazil, showing how language, territory and power are intertwined in the production of narratives about the past.

2. Theoretical Reference

2.1. The Tupi-Guarani matrix and the notion of territory

Understanding the territorial organization of the Tupi-Guarani peoples requires moving away from fixed Western conceptions of space, often associated with static delimitation and property. Among the Guarani, the territory is not configured as a rigidly defined unit, but as a lived space, crossed by symbolic, spiritual relations and practices of mobility. In this sense, the concept of territory is closer to a network of meanings and paths than to a delimited geographical area.

According to Bartomeu Melià, the Guarani experience is deeply linked to the idea of "walking", with displacement being a constitutive element of its cosmology and social organization⁴. Movement, far from representing instability, translates a form of relationship with the world, in which space is continuously produced by the trajectories of individuals and groups. Thus, the paths (*tapé*) are not only means of displacement, but fundamental structures of territorial organization.

From this perspective, Guarani mobility should not be interpreted as nomadism in the classical sense, but as a form of territorialization, based on circulation between different points of reference, such as villages, cultivation areas and sacred spaces. Such dynamics evidence a flexible territorial logic, in which space is constructed through practice and collective memory.

Complementing this reading, Eduardo Viveiros de Castro proposes that Amerindian cosmologies operate from a relational ontology, in which the distinction between nature and culture is not presented in Western molds⁵. This approach allows us to understand the indigenous territory as a field of relations, where humans, non-humans and elements of the landscape are articulated in an integrated way. In this context, the paths assume not only a practical function, but also a symbolic one, connecting different dimensions of existence.

2.2. Language, etymology and identity construction

Language plays a central role in the construction and transmission of collective identities, especially in indigenous contexts, in which orality and the naming of spaces constitute fundamental forms of organization of the world. The term *tapé*, of Tupi-Guarani origin,

⁴ MELIÀ, Bartomeu. *The Guarani conquered and reduced*, 1986.

⁵ VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, Eduardo. *The inconstancy of the wild soul*, 2002.

exemplifies this relationship by designating simultaneously a physical element — the path — and a symbolic dimension — the connection between places and experiences.

The attribution of the term "Tapes" to the Guarani groups that inhabited certain regions of southern Brazil reveals a process of identification based on territorial and functional characteristics. In this case, language acts as a mediator between space and identity, converting a practice — the use of paths — into a collective marker.

According to Manuela Carneiro da Cunha, naming processes in colonial contexts often involve power relations, in which external groups assign denominations that may not correspond to the forms of self-definition of native peoples⁶. This dynamic often results in simplifications or generalizations that obscure the internal diversity of these groups.

In the case of the Tapes, it is observed that the designation, initially linked to a specific territorial characteristic, was progressively expanded and resignified by the European colonizers. This process evidences the transformation of an indigenous term into a colonial category, loaded with new meanings and inserted in a logic of domination and control.

2.3. Indigenous territoriality and circulation networks

Before the arrival of the Europeans, the South American territory was already structured by complex circulation networks established by indigenous peoples⁷. These networks, formed by trails and paths, allowed the connection between different regions, facilitating the exchange of goods, information and cultural practices. In this context, paths played a role similar to that of infrastructures, articulating spaces and enabling territorial integration.

In the south of present-day Brazil, the region associated with the Tapes stood out as an important axis connecting the interior and the coast, functioning as a natural corridor for various displacements. This strategic condition contributed to its subsequent valorization by colonial agents, who began to use and adapt these routes to their own interests.

The incorporation of these paths into the colonial system did not occur in a neutral way. On the contrary, it implied the reconfiguration of their meanings and uses, subordinating them to new economic and political dynamics. Thus, what, in the indigenous context, represented a network of relations and mobility, came to be interpreted as a logistical resource and an instrument of territorial control.

This transition highlights one of the central aspects of the colonial process: the appropriation of pre-existing structures and their redefinition within a different logic. In the case of the Tapes, the paths that defined their identity and territorial organization became, paradoxically, elements that facilitated their own subordination and historical transformation.

⁶ CUNHA, Manuela Carneiro da. *História dos Índios no Brasil*, 1992.

⁷ NOELLI, Francisco Silva. USP Magazine, 1999.

3. Historical Context of the Tapes

3.1. The Guarani in Southern Brazil

The presence of the Guarani peoples in southern Brazil is part of a broad process of territorial expansion that took place over the centuries, prior to the arrival of the Europeans⁸. These groups, belonging to the Tupi-Guarani linguistic trunk, occupied extensive areas of South America, distributed in regions that today correspond to southern Brazil, Paraguay, Argentina and Bolivia.

In the current territory of Rio Grande do Sul, the Guarani settled predominantly in plateau areas and regions close to watercourses, which offered favorable conditions for agriculture, gathering and mobility. Its social organization was based on relatively autonomous villages, articulated by kinship ties, political alliances and circulation networks. Agriculture, especially the cultivation of cassava, corn and yerba mate, coexisted with hunting, fishing and gathering practices, composing a diversified economic system adapted to the environment.

The dynamics of Guarani occupation was characterized by a balance between settlement and mobility. Villages could be relocated over time, either for environmental reasons or for social or spiritual motivations. This pattern reinforces the understanding that the territory, for these groups, was not defined by rigid limits, but by a network of interconnected spaces, among which displacements played a fundamental role.

3.2. The Serra dos Tapes region

The area that would later be called "Serra dos Tapes" is located to the west of Lagoa dos Patos, covering regions of gently undulating relief and areas of transition between the plateau and the coastal plain. This geographical configuration favored circulation between the interior and the coast, making the region a strategic point for displacements and exchanges.

Before the colonial occupation, this region was already configured as an important axis of passage, integrating different indigenous territories through trails and paths consolidated over time. These routes not only connected villages, but also allowed access to natural resources and spaces of symbolic significance.

With the arrival of Europeans, this strategic characteristic was quickly recognized and incorporated into colonial dynamics. The region has come to be seen as a natural corridor, essential for the circulation of people, goods and information. Such recognition contributed to the consolidation of the term "Tape zone", which synthesized the territorial function of this space.

The name "Serra dos Tapes", in turn, emerges in this context as a form of geographical identification that directly associates the territory with the indigenous groups that

⁸ NOELLI, Francisco Silva. USP Magazine, 1999.

inhabited it. It is, therefore, a construction that articulates space and identity, reflecting both indigenous perception and colonial interpretation.

3.3. The Tapes as "Indians of the path"

The designation "Tapes" applied to the Guarani groups of the region cannot be understood as a self-denomination in the strict sense, but rather as a category constructed from the observation of their territorial practices. Derived from the term *tapé*, the expression refers directly to the idea of path, evidencing the centrality of mobility in the organization of these groups.

By being identified as "Indians of the path", the Tapes come to be defined not only by their ethnic origin, but by their relationship with space and circulation routes. This association reveals a fundamental aspect of the way European colonizers interpreted and categorized indigenous peoples: based on perceived functions within the colonial territorial logic.

However, this external reading simplifies a more complex reality. For the Guarani themselves, the paths were not mere instruments of displacement, but constitutive elements of their social and spiritual existence. Thus, the reduction of this dimension to a functional category represents a process of cultural translation that, while allowing communication between different worlds, also produces distortions and erasures.

With the advance of colonization, especially from the seventeenth century onwards, the term "Tapes" began to be widely used to designate both the indigenous people of the region and the territory itself. This semantic expansion evidences a process of generalization that contributes to the dilution of the cultural specificities of these groups, inserting them into broader and more homogeneous categories.

In this way, the historical construction of the "Tapes" as an identity reveals itself to be inseparable from the dynamics of contact, conflict and appropriation that marked the colonial period. What was initially presented as a reference to indigenous mobility progressively became an instrument of classification and control, inserted in a logic external to the very peoples it sought to describe.

4. The Jesuit Missions and the Region of the Tapes

4.1. The performance of the Society of Jesus

The activities of the Society of Jesus in South America, from the seventeenth century onwards, are part of the broader context of Iberian colonial expansion and the consolidation of territorial occupation strategies⁹. In the case of the Tapes region, the Jesuit presence was not limited to the evangelization of indigenous peoples, but constituted a complex project of social, spatial and cultural reorganization.

The Jesuit missionaries, when establishing contact with the Guarani groups, identified in the community organization of these peoples elements that could be adapted to the model

⁹ POMPA, Cristina. *Religion as Translation*, 2003.

of reductions. This process involved both the translation of Christian concepts into the indigenous symbolic universe and the reconfiguration of everyday practices, including work, housing, and forms of authority.

However, this interaction did not occur in a homogeneous or passive manner. Adherence to the missions varied according to local contexts, strategic interests, and forms of resistance. For many groups, the approach to the Jesuits also represented an alternative of protection against the incursions of bandeirantes, who advanced on the region with the aim of capturing indigenous people for forced labor.

In this sense, the Jesuit reductions can be understood as ambiguous spaces: at the same time that they promoted a certain protection and stability, they also implied the introduction of new forms of control and discipline, aligned with colonial and religious interests¹⁰.

4.2. The reductions in the Tape region (from 1626)

The foundation of the first reductions in the Tapes region, from 1626 onwards, marked a decisive moment in the historical configuration of southern Brazil. These missions, established in strategically located areas, sought to concentrate indigenous populations in nuclei organized according to Christian and European principles.

The structure of the reductions was based on a relatively standardized model, with a central square, church, collective housing and areas for agricultural production. This spatial organization reflected a logic of planning that contrasted with the traditional territorial dynamics of the Guarani, characterized by dispersion and mobility.

From an economic point of view, the missions developed agricultural and artisanal activities that guaranteed relative autonomy, while integrating themselves into colonial networks. On the cultural level, they promoted an intense process of catechizing, in which elements of indigenous religiosity were reinterpreted or suppressed.

The Tapes region, due to its strategic position, became an important missionary nucleus, being often referred to as "Missions of the Tapes". This denomination reinforces the association between territory and identity, now mediated by the Jesuit presence and the structure of the reductions.

4.3. Transformations in the indigenous structure

The implementation of the Jesuit missions implied profound transformations in the social and territorial organization of the Guarani groups in the Tapes region. One of the most significant aspects was the transition from a logic of mobility to a model of sedentarization, in which displacements began to be regulated and, in many cases, restricted.

This change directly affected the relationship of the indigenous people with the territory. The paths, previously central to the organization of Guarani life, lost part of their

¹⁰ KERN, Arno Alvarez, 1982.

structural role, being replaced by a spatiality centered on reduction. What was once a circulation network has become a sedentary structure.

In addition, the introduction of new forms of authority—represented by missionaries and co-opted indigenous leaders—has altered the internal dynamics of communities. Social organization began to be guided by external norms, which redefined roles, behaviors, and cultural practices.

On the symbolic level, this process resulted in a reconfiguration of identity references. Elements of Guarani cosmology were reinterpreted in the light of Christian doctrine, producing hybrid forms of religiosity, but also generating tensions and resistance.

In this way, the Jesuit missions in the region of the Tapes cannot be understood only as spaces of evangelization, but as devices for territorial and cultural reorganization. By transforming the relationship of indigenous people with space – especially with the paths that structured their existence – they contributed to the redefinition of the very meaning of "Tapes", inserting it in a new logic of control and domination.

5. Bandeirantes and the Redefinition of the Term "Tapes"

5.1. São Paulo's expansion and incursions to the south

From the first half of the seventeenth century, the Tapes region became part of the field of action of the bandeirante expeditions from the captaincy of São Paulo¹¹. These incursions, motivated mainly by the capture of indigenous people for compulsory labor, advanced on territories occupied by Guarani groups and on the reductions established by the Society of Jesus.

The bandeirantes, when entering the south of the colonial territory, found in the Jesuit missions a significant concentration of indigenous population, which made them strategic targets. Between the 1620s and 1640s, several reductions were attacked, resulting in the dispersion of communities, the capture of thousands of indigenous people, and the dismantling of social structures that had recently been reorganized under missionary influence.

These actions not only compromised the stability of the missions, but also intensified the flows of forced displacement, disrupting previously established territorial networks. In this process, the Tapes region ceased to be just a space of circulation structured by the indigenous people themselves and became part of a logic of violent exploitation, marked by instability and external imposition.

5.2. Colonial appropriation of the nomenclature

Parallel to the territorial and social transformations, there is a process of appropriation and re-signification of the term "Tapes" by the Portuguese colonizers. Initially linked to

¹¹ MONTEIRO, John Manuel, 1994.

the indigenous notion of path (*tapé*) and to the identification of specific groups, the term began to be used in a broader and more generic way.

In the context of the bandeirante expeditions, "Tapes" came to designate not only the indigenous people associated with the region, but also the territory itself and, in certain cases, any indigenous group located in that area. This semantic broadening reflects a logic of simplification and categorization typical of colonial processes, in which cultural diversity is often reduced to broader and functionally useful classifications.

This linguistic transformation evidences a shift in meaning: from an expression rooted in the indigenous experience of mobility and territoriality to an external category, used as an instrument of identification and, to a certain extent, of control. When incorporated into the colonial vocabulary, the term loses part of its original symbolic density, starting to operate within a logic different from that which originated it.

5.3. Erasure and identity reconstruction

The process of re-signification of the term "Tapes" is directly associated with broader dynamics of erasure and identity reconstruction that marked the colonization of the region. The destruction of the missions, the dispersion of indigenous populations, and the imposition of new social structures contributed to the fragmentation of original collective identities.

In this context, the designation "Tapes" starts to function as a residual category, which preserves traces of a previous reality, but already profoundly transformed. At the same time, its permanence in the historical and geographical vocabulary indicates the persistence of a memory, even if mediated by colonial interpretations.

The reconstruction of identity, in turn, occurs in the midst of these tensions, involving processes of adaptation, resistance and reinterpretation. Elements of the Guarani culture continue to exist, albeit in new forms, demonstrating the resilience of these peoples in the face of the imposed transformations.

In this way, the trajectory of the term "Tapes" — from its origin in the Tupi-Guarani universe to its incorporation into colonial discourse — reveals not only a change in meaning, but a broader process of symbolic dispute. It is an example of how language, power and territory are articulated in the construction of historical narratives, showing that words, as well as the spaces they designate, are also fields of conflict.

6. Analysis: Way, Power, and Narrative

The historical trajectory of the term "Tapes", from its origin in the Tupi-Guarani word *tapé* to its incorporation into colonial discourse, allows us to understand how language, territory and power are articulated in the construction of historical narratives. More than a simple geographical or ethnic designation, "Tapes" reveals itself as a category in dispute, whose meaning was progressively transformed as different agents began to intervene in the space and in the peoples who inhabited it.

In the Guarani universe, the "path" was not restricted to a utilitarian function. It constituted a structuring element of existence, articulating mobility, sociability and spirituality. The routes established by the indigenous groups organized the territory as a living network of relationships, in which displacement was an integral part of the construction of the world. In this sense, the *tapé* represented not only a means, but a way of being and inhabiting the space.

With the arrival of the Europeans – especially through the work of the Society of Jesus – this territorial logic began to be strained by a project that aimed to reorganize space and populations according to different principles. The Jesuit reductions, by promoting the sedentarization and centralization of indigenous communities, operated a significant rupture in the dynamics of the roads. What was once flow has become fixation; what was a network became a nucleus; what was autonomy began to be regulated.

This process can be interpreted as a form of reconfiguration of the territory through symbolic and material control. By redefining modes of occupation and circulation, the missions not only transformed physical space, but also the meanings associated with it. The "path", as a structuring element of Guarani territoriality, lost centrality in the face of a new logic that favored stability, vigilance and hierarchical organization.

Subsequently, with the bandeirante incursions and the intensification of the Portuguese colonial presence, this reconfiguration was deepened and redirected. The appropriation of the term "Tapes" as a generic category evidences a second movement of transformation: the capture of language as an instrument of power. By naming, classifying, and generalizing, colonial discourse not only describes reality, but reorganizes it according to its own references.

In this sense, the redefinition of "Tapes" can be understood as part of a broader process of symbolic domination, in which the elements of indigenous culture are reinterpreted and incorporated into a narrative that displaces them from their original context. It is an operation that, while preserving the form — the term — profoundly alters its content.

This dynamic dialogues directly with the understanding that historical processes are not limited to the material occupation of the territory, but also involve the dispute for meanings. Language, in this context, acts as a strategic field, in which identities are defined, practices are legitimized, and versions of the past are constructed.

When analyzing the case of the Tapes, it becomes evident that the "path" — initially an expression of mobility and connection — was progressively converted into an instrument of control and classification. This transformation reveals a symbolic inversion: what structured indigenous autonomy began to be used, directly or indirectly, for their subordination.

In this way, the term "Tapes" is no longer just a historical reference and becomes an entry point for understanding the relations between power, territory and narrative. Its trajectory shows how apparently descriptive categories can carry deep layers of meaning, reflecting processes of dispute, appropriation and re-signification.

By bringing this analysis, this article proposes not only to revisit the history of the Tapes, but to question the ways in which this history was constructed and transmitted. In this movement, it seeks to recover, albeit partially, the original density of indigenous concepts, recognizing them as central elements — and not peripheral — in the historical formation of southern Brazil.

7. Metodologia

The present study is characterized as a qualitative research, with a historical-interpretative approach, focused on the analysis of the construction and transformation of the term "Tapes" in the context of the territorial and cultural formation of southern Brazil. The investigation seeks to understand not only the historical events related to the Guarani groups in the region, but also the processes of linguistic and symbolic redefinition associated with colonization.

From the point of view of technical procedures, the research is based on bibliographic review and documentary analysis. The bibliographic review covers works in the areas of History, Anthropology and Linguistics, with emphasis on studies on Tupi-Guarani peoples, indigenous territoriality and Jesuit missions. Among the main theoretical references, contributions from authors such as Bartomeu Melià, Eduardo Viveiros de Castro and Manuela Carneiro da Cunha stand out, whose approaches allow a critical reading of the relations between culture, language and territory¹².

Documentary analysis, in turn, considers historical sources related to the colonial period, including reports from missionaries, Jesuit correspondence, and records produced in the context of the reductions. These documents are examined with the aim of identifying how the term "Tapes" was used, interpreted and transformed over time, especially in the contact between indigenous people and colonial agents, such as the Society of Jesus and the bandeirantes.

The methodological approach adopted is analytical-interpretative, seeking to articulate historical data and theoretical reflections in the construction of a critical narrative. In this sense, the study is not limited to the description of the facts, but seeks to understand the meanings underlying the transformations observed, especially with regard to the relationship between language, power and territoriality.

In addition, the research assumes an interdisciplinary character, by dialoguing with different fields of knowledge, which enables a more comprehensive understanding of the object of study. History contributes to the contextualization of colonial processes; Anthropology offers instruments for the analysis of indigenous cultures; and Linguistics helps in understanding the semantic transformations of the term in question.

Finally, it is emphasized that the interpretation of the data is guided by a critical perspective, which seeks to problematize traditional narratives and highlight indigenous

¹² MELIÀ, Bartomeu. *El Guaraní conquistado y reducido*, 1986. VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, Eduardo. *The inconstancy of the wild soul*, 2002. CUNHA, Manuela Carneiro da. *História dos Índios no Brasil*, 1992.

protagonism in the historical construction of the region. This methodological stance aims not only to broaden the understanding of the term "Tapes", but also to contribute to the debate on the processes of production of historical knowledge.

8. Results and Discussion

The analysis developed throughout this study allows us to identify that the term "Tapes", far from constituting a simple geographical or ethnic designation, expresses a complex historical process, marked by semantic, territorial and symbolic transformations. From its origin in the Tupi-Guarani word *tapé*, it can be observed that its initial meaning was deeply linked to the notion of path as a structuring element of indigenous territoriality¹³.

In the Guarani context, the paths configured circulation networks that articulated different spaces and dimensions of social, economic and spiritual life. This territorial logic, based on mobility and interconnection, evidences a form of organization different from that introduced by colonial agents. In this sense, the so-called Tapes should not be understood only as a specific grouping, but as part of a broader territorial dynamic, in which displacement played a central role.

With the action of the Society of Jesus and the implementation of reductions from 1626 onwards, a first significant inflection in this model can be observed. The sedentarization of indigenous populations and the spatial reorganization of communities implied the redefinition of relations with the territory, shifting the axis from mobility to settlement. The paths, previously central, began to occupy a secondary role within a new logic of control and ordering.

Subsequently, the bandeirante incursions deepened this process of transformation, promoting the dismantling of the missions and the dispersion of the indigenous populations. In this context, the term "Tapes" came to be appropriated by the Portuguese colonial discourse, acquiring a broader and more generic character. This re-signification evidences the transformation of a category rooted in the indigenous experience into an instrument of external classification, aligned with the interests of colonization.

The articulation between these different historical moments allows us to understand that the trajectory of the term "Tapes" is directly related to the power disputes that marked the occupation of the southern territory. Language, in this process, plays a central role, functioning as a means of translation, but also as an instrument of symbolic domination. By redefining the meanings associated with space and indigenous groups, colonial discourse contributed to the construction of a narrative that, in many cases, obscures the complexity of the original dynamics.

The results obtained indicate, therefore, that the analysis of the term "Tapes" enables a broader understanding of the relations between territory, identity and power. By highlighting the transformations undergone by this category over time, the study reveals

¹³ MELIÀ, Bartomeu. *The Guarani conquered and reduced*, 1986.

how historical processes of occupation and control are also reflected in the language and forms of naming.

In addition, the discussion points to the need to critically revisit the categories used by traditional historiography, recognizing that many of them are products of specific contexts of domination. In the case of the Tapes, this revision makes it possible to recover, albeit partially, the original symbolic density of the concept of *tapé*, placing indigenous protagonism at the center of the analysis.

Thus, the present study contributes to the deepening of the debate on the historical formation of southern Brazil, by demonstrating that the understanding of the past requires not only the analysis of events, but also the problematization of the languages and narratives that describe them.

9. Final Considerations

This article sought to analyze the origin, evolution and historical implications of the term "Tapes", evidencing its relationship with the territoriality of the Guarani peoples and with the transformation processes resulting from colonization in southern Brazil. Starting from the understanding of the Tupi-Guarani word *tapé* as an expression of path, trail or road, it was possible to identify that its original meaning was deeply rooted in a territorial logic based on mobility, circulation and interconnection between spaces.

Throughout the analysis, it was found that the groups called "Tapes" did not constitute only a delimited ethnic category, but were part of a broader territorial dynamic, in which the paths played a structuring role. This configuration was significantly altered with the action of the Society of Jesus, which, through the Jesuit reductions, promoted the sedentarization and spatial reorganization of the indigenous populations, introducing new forms of control and order.

Subsequently, the bandeirante incursions contributed to the disarticulation of these structures and to the intensification of the processes of forced displacement, consolidating a new stage of territorial and social transformation. In this context, the term "Tapes" was appropriated by the Portuguese colonial discourse, coming to designate more broadly both the indigenous people and the territory, evidencing a process of re-signification that displaced its original meaning.

Thus, it is concluded that the trajectory of the term "Tapes" reveals a continuous movement of transformation, in which language, territory and power are intertwined. What initially expressed a form of spatial and symbolic organization of the Guarani peoples was progressively incorporated and redefined by external agents, becoming part of a logic of classification and control.

The analysis carried out demonstrates that the understanding of the historical formation of southern Brazil requires an approach that goes beyond the description of the events, incorporating reflection on the processes of construction of the categories used to interpret them. In this sense, the study contributes to the historiographical debate by highlighting

the need to problematize traditional narratives and recognize indigenous protagonism in the configuration of territories and circulation networks.

Finally, it is emphasized that the recovery of the conceptual density of terms such as *tapé* not only enriches historical understanding, but also opens space for new interpretations of the relations between culture, language, and power. Thus, the case of the Tapes reveals itself as a relevant starting point for future investigations that seek to deepen the analysis of indigenous and colonial dynamics in the South American context.

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